

Qualia from quantum magic: A quantum resource approach to phenomenal consciousness

Gandhimohan M. Viswanathan

Department of Physics, Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte, 59078-970 Natal-RN, Brazil

(Dated: September 1, 2025)

Qualia—the first-person qualities of subjective experiences that constitute the “what it is like” of phenomenal consciousness—have thus far resisted physical explanation. Here we hypothesize that qualia are generated in the brain during the quantum computational resolution of difficult inverse problems when non-Clifford magic states are consumed above a threshold rate. Magic states are a well-known quantum resource necessary for universal quantum computation—a form of computational fuel. Inverse problems in cognition, such as reconstructing the state of the environment or internal states from incomplete or noisy sensory and interoceptive data, are typically ill-posed and computationally costly. A prototypical inverse problem is determining the actual 3D shape of an object from a blurry 2D retinal image. The Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis reframes classic philosophical thought experiments (e.g., zombies and inverted qualia), predicts when and where qualia should arise, and offers a natural explanation for their absence in simple systems such as thermostats and in many complex systems such as the Internet. In the brain, it predicts consciousness-related activity to be concentrated in the posterior sensory cortices, because vision and hearing pose some of the most challenging inverse problems that are vital to an animal’s survival. In light of this prediction, we conclude by discussing recent empirical findings of the Cogitate Consortium.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17021675>

I. INTRODUCTION

The hard problem of consciousness remains one of the most important open problems in science. Indeed, phenomenal consciousness—the subjective or “what it is like” aspect of first-person experience [1]—continues to elude broadly accepted scientific explanations [2, 3]. The term “qualia” is the plural of quale, an individual’s subjective quality of a particular conscious experience. Qualia are what it feels like from the inside, the internally experienced qualities typically associated with raw sensory inputs. The hard problem, as formulated by Chalmers [4], specifically addresses the challenge of explaining why and how physical processes in the brain generate subjective experience in the first place. This stands in contrast to the “easy” problems of consciousness, which concern objective functions like perception, memory, and behavior, and can, in principle, be investigated without appealing to phenomenal experience.

Some of the leading theories of consciousness are Integrated Information Theory (IIT) [5, 6], Global Workspace Theory (GWT) and the closely related Global Neuronal Workspace Theory (GNWT) [7–9]. IIT proposes that consciousness corresponds to the amount of integrated information generated by a system, aiming to quantify subjective experience itself. It assumes that consciousness is a fundamental entity having causal power. GWT describes consciousness as resulting from the global availability of information within a cognitive workspace. IIT, GWT, GNWT and similar approaches have found success explaining certain aspects of consciousness and are reviewed below. However, there

is at present no widely accepted theory of consciousness that is considered fully satisfactory [10] (see Sec. III). In this context, this work proposes a different angle of attack on the hard problem of consciousness, one rooted in (quantum) resource theory.

We begin by pointing out that qualia are not arbitrary, but rather arise only in specific circumstances (Table I). To illustrate this specificity, recall Ramachandran and Hirstein’s heuristics known as the *Three Laws of Qualia* [11], which present a concise operational framework for characterizing their occurrence: (i) irrevocability (e.g., red sunsets are never perceived as blue), (ii) behavioral flexibility (e.g., the choice of a fight-vs.-flight decision given incomplete or uncertain data), and (iii) persistence in working memory (e.g., a memorable romantic encounter). Thus, qualia are likely associated with highly specific neural circuitry (Table II). Indeed, much effort has been devoted to identifying the neural correlates of consciousness [12], and notable progress has been made [13]. Here, we focus on a different question: what kinds of cognitive processes are associated with qualia? A partial answer is hinted by the Three Laws of Qualia, which raise the possibility that such experiences are tied to resource-intensive cognitive processes. Optimal decision making may require inferring internal or external states from ambiguous, noisy, or incomplete sensory data.

In mathematical and computational terms, these kinds of challenges fall under the category of inverse problems—inferring the unknown inputs or parameters of a system given data consisting of its noisy or incomplete outputs, for instance, determining the actual 3D shape of an object from a blurry 2D

retinal image. Inverse problems are typically ill-posed and more computationally costly than direct problems [14]. Solving them often requires optimization under uncertainty and robustness to noise [15]. These challenges impose high computational demands, particularly in high-dimensional or nonlinear settings. Quantum computing, under specific conditions, has the potential to provide significant (and in rare cases even exponential) speedups for solving many structured optimization tasks [16, 17].

The computational speedup conferred by a quantum computer is not automatic or guaranteed. To outperform classical algorithms in a fault-tolerant setting, the computing system must exploit resources that enable universal quantum computation—notably, non-Clifford operations [18–20]. Magic states are an example of a non-Clifford resource—precisely the kind needed to go beyond dynamics that are efficiently simulable classically [21–23]. Without non-Clifford resources, quantum computation is limited to operations that can be efficiently simulated on a classical computer (see Sec. II). Crucially, magic states in sufficient quantities can potentially unlock a significant quantum advantage.

In this work, we propose that qualia arise specifically during the quantum computational resolution of difficult inverse problems, contingent on the consumption of non-Clifford magic states. The Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis predicts where qualia should occur, offers a natural explanation for their absence in systems that do not perform such quantum computations (e.g., classical computers and networks), and provides new perspectives on thought experiments such as the philosophical zombie and inverted color qualia (see Sec. IV). In the brain, it predicts consciousness-related activity to be prominent in the posterior sensory cortices, because vision and hearing both require the solution of inverse problems.

The skeptical reader may object that quantum phenomena cannot be relevant in a hot and noisy brain, but there is growing empirical evidence suggesting that quantum effects may indeed play a role in neural processing. In 2018, Kerskens and Pérez applied nuclear magnetic resonance techniques to detect consciousness-dependent zero-quantum coherence signals in the brain, which the authors suggest may indicate that certain brain functions operate non-classically [24]. In 2020, Smith *et al.* [25] explored the role of radical pairs in xenon-induced general anesthesia to explain the surprising finding by Li *et al.* [26] that isotopes with non-zero nuclear spin exhibit reduced anesthetic potency compared to those with zero nuclear spin. It is unlikely that the small mass differences in the xenon isotopes are causing these effects, so the findings taken together provide both theoretical and experimental evidence consistent with the involvement of (non-classical) quantum mechanical effects in xenon-induced anesthesia. In 2024, Babcock *et al.* studied UV-excited tryptophan networks and found that they can exhibit superradiant photon emission [27]. It is worth recalling that tryptophan is the precursor in the

Table I. Qualia and behavior. According to the heuristics known as the Three Laws of Qualia [11], they are typically irrevocable (e.g., blue is never red), usually allow behavioral flexibility (e.g., fight vs. flight), and often are associated with persistent memories (e.g., that awkward moment at the social event). Activities without qualia (e.g., autonomic processes) typically do not exhibit these features.

Activity	Qualia	Irrev.	Flex.	Memory
Seeing a color	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Hearing music	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Feeling pain	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Smelling a flower	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Tasting chocolate	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Autonomic digestion of food	No	No	No	No
Sweating to cool body	No	No	No	No
Regulating blood pressure	No	No	No	No
Fingernail growth	No	No	No	No

brain of serotonin and melatonin and is also closely related to ergoline-derived and tryptamine psychedelics, such as LSD and DMT. Moreover, superradiance is a quantum phenomenon with non-classical collective behavior. Their possible occurrence in microtubules suggests a potential role for quantum optical phenomena in cellular signaling and neuroprotein function. Also in 2024, Khan *et al.* studied the effect of the microtubule-stabilizing agent epothilone B on anesthesia in rats and found that it prolonged the onset of unconsciousness induced by isoflurane [28]. The results suggest that microtubule integrity is relevant to anesthesia, in a manner compatible with the ORCH-OR theory proposed by Penrose [29] and Hameroff [30], according to which microtubules may serve as possible sites of quantum processes inside neurons [30] (see Sec. III).

In what follows, Sec. II gives a brief review of magic states. Sec. III presents the main existing approaches to the problem of consciousness and highlights their strengths and possible limitations. The Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis is presented in Sec. IV. Sec. V lists some of the main limitations of the hypothesis and ends by discussing very recent empirical findings of the Cogitate Consortium.

II. QUANTUM MAGIC STATES

Magic states are a non-Clifford quantum resource. Quantum computers can perform certain computations without specialized resources, but these are efficiently simulable classically [21–23]. The introduction of non-Clifford resources enables the implementation of operations necessary for universal quantum advantage. Although computations without such resources are

Table II. Brain Regions and Qualia. Some regions are very important while others seem to have less relevance to qualia [8, 31–34].

Qualia Region	Description	Non-Qualia Region	Description
Visual Cortex	Critical for visual qualia such as color and shape perception; lesions often cause blindness or visual deficits.	Cerebellum	Primarily responsible for motor coordination and learning; damage affects movement but usually spares conscious experience.
Somatosensory Cortex	Processes tactile qualia including touch and pain; damage can cause loss or alteration of somatic sensations.	Basal Ganglia	Involved in movement control and procedural memory; not directly linked to the generation of qualia.
Auditory Cortex	Essential for auditory qualia including perception of sounds and music; lesions can impair hearing and auditory experience.	Brainstem	Regulates arousal and wakefulness; necessary for consciousness level but not the content of qualia.
Insular Cortex	Involved in interoceptive awareness and emotional qualia, integrating visceral sensations with subjective feeling.	Corpus Callosum	Connects the two cerebral hemispheres; damage causes split-brain effects but qualia apparently persist within hemispheres.
Prefrontal Cortex	Linked to higher-order aspects of consciousness, working memory, and the persistence of qualia.	Primary Motor Cortex	Controls voluntary movements; damage impairs motor function but typically spares conscious qualia.

possible, they are essentially “classical,” in a sense that can be made precise. Specifically, a quantum computer without non-Clifford resources will be limited to the computing power of a classical Turing machine—such a “quantum” computer cannot solve any problem that a classical computer cannot. Thus, such resources are essential for unlocking the full computational power of quantum computational devices. We give a brief review of the subject.

Universal classical computing was famously formalized in terms of Turing machines. In classical computing, universal computation is possible through use of Boolean logic gates, such as AND, OR, NOT, that can be combined to implement any (classical) algorithmic process. Classical computers are bounded by two constraints: (i) the practical limits imposed by the laws of physics that govern their hardware, and (ii) the theoretical limits of the Turing machine model they implement, which processes information in definite states rather than linear superpositions of states.

On the other hand, universal quantum computing uses quantum bits—qubits—that can represent linear superpositions of the classical bit values 0 and 1. Take for example a system that can exist in two states, $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. If this two-level system is used to represent classical bits, then the state of the system is either $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$. But in quantum mechanics, the state of the system could be any (properly normalized) linear superposition $|\psi\rangle$ of the two states,

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|a|^2 + |b|^2}} (a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle), \quad (1)$$

where a and b are any two complex-valued numbers. Given the normalization constraint and assuming that the overall global phase factor is not relevant, there remain exactly two free real-valued parameters, which may be chosen to be equivalent to two angles:

$$|\psi\rangle = \cos(\theta/2) |0\rangle + e^{i\phi} \sin(\theta/2) |1\rangle. \quad (2)$$

This representation is known as the Bloch sphere [16], see Figure 1. Qubits can also exhibit quantum entanglement, whereby two or more qubits exist in a non-separable state—a joint state that cannot be expressed as a product of the individual qubit states. Entanglement is also a quantum resource, but it is not directly related to the subject matter of this work. We refer the interested reader to ref. [16].

An N -bit classical system can be in one of 2^N states. In contrast, an N -qubit quantum system can exist in a superposition of up to 2^N computational basis states. These properties, combined with quantum interference and entanglement, allow quantum computers to perform certain computations more efficiently than classical computers, especially for problems with specific mathematical structure. A trade-off can be considered between using a classical computer and a quantum computer that exploits the special properties of quantum states. Understanding this trade-off motivates the study of quantum magic states, for which a prerequisite is basic knowledge of Clifford gates and the Clifford group.

Recall that in algebra, a group is a set together with a binary operation that is associative, has an identity element, and where every element has an inverse. Since

Figure 1. Classical computers operate on bits that only have two states, $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. A quantum computer, however, operates on qubits that can be any linear superposition $|\psi\rangle = \cos(\theta/2) |0\rangle + e^{i\phi} \sin(\theta/2) |1\rangle$. Such a pure qubit can be represented as a point on the Bloch sphere, shown above. A mixed state corresponds to a point strictly inside the sphere. An N -qubit pure state can be represented as a point on a high-dimensional manifold in a complex projective Hilbert space.

a single qubit is a vector in a two-dimensional Hilbert space, it can be expressed as a linear combination of two orthonormal basis states. Following convention, let the basis states of \mathbb{C}^2 be represented as

$$|0\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad |1\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

Next, consider the Pauli matrices σ_i , with the identity $\sigma_0 = \mathbb{I}$ included:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_0 &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \sigma_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \sigma_2 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{bmatrix}, & \sigma_3 &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

It is an easy exercise to check that iterative multiplication of these matrices among themselves produces a closed set of 16 matrices:

$$\{\pm\sigma_0, \pm i\sigma_0, \pm\sigma_1, \pm i\sigma_1, \pm\sigma_2, \pm i\sigma_2, \pm\sigma_3, \pm i\sigma_3\}. \quad (5)$$

This set of 16 elements satisfies the criteria for a group, and is known as the Pauli group G_1 . Note that the phase factors $\{\pm 1, \pm i\}$ are essential for group closure. We say that, together with the scalar multiples $\{\pm 1, \pm i\}$, the Pauli operators generate G_1 . More generally, the Pauli group G_n is generated under matrix multiplication by all

n -fold tensor products of the one-qubit Pauli matrices $\{\sigma_0, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3\}$ together with the phase factors $\{\pm 1, \pm i\}$, acting on the Hilbert space $(\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$. Since the Pauli operators are unitary, the Pauli group G_n is a subgroup of the unitary group $U(2^n)$ of $2^n \times 2^n$ matrices.

In group theory, given a set $S \subseteq G$ of a group G , the normalizer $N_G(S)$ of S in G is the set of all $g \in G$ such that the cosets gS and Sg are identical, in other words, $gSg^{-1} = g^{-1}Sg = S$. We say that S is invariant under conjugation by g . If a subgroup $S \subseteq G$ is invariant under conjugation by all $g \in G$, then S is known as a normal subgroup of G . For any (not necessarily normal) subgroup $S \subseteq G$, the normalizer $N_G(S)$ of S in G is defined as the largest subgroup in G of which S is a normal subgroup. Obviously, $S \subseteq N_G(S)$. The Clifford group \mathbf{C}_n for n qubits is the normalizer of the Pauli group in the unitary group, i.e, it is the largest subgroup of $U(2^n)$ in which the Pauli group G_n is normal. So G_n is invariant under conjugation by elements of \mathbf{C}_n .

Since the elements of the Pauli and Clifford groups can be represented in terms of unitary matrices that can act on qubits, they can be used to represent gate operations that take one state to another. Conventionally, the X , Y and Z gates act on a single qubit according to

$$X = \sigma_1, \quad Y = \sigma_2, \quad Z = \sigma_3. \quad (6)$$

Gates corresponding to the other elements of the Pauli group G_1 can be obtained by combining the X , Y , and Z gates, because the Pauli matrices generate G_1 (along with the previously mentioned phase factors, though usually, in practice quantum gates are defined only up to the global phase factors). A Clifford gate that acts on one qubit, analogously, is one whose operation is given by some element of the Clifford group \mathbf{C}_1 . Multi-qubit Clifford gates correspond to elements of the Clifford group \mathbf{C}_n .

A crucial fact about Clifford gates is that, given either $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ as an input, they are unable to output an arbitrary state $|\psi\rangle$ on the Bloch sphere (2). Clifford gates can only take the basis states $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$ to a small set of points on the Bloch sphere known as stabilizer states. In fact, in terms of surface area on the Bloch sphere, stabilizer states form a finite set of measure zero. This fact merits explanation, since it is related to the importance of magic states.

Consider first the X gate, given by the Pauli matrix σ_1 . It is easy to check X acts on a qubit as a rotation of π radians on the Bloch sphere, apart from a global phase factor, $|0\rangle \longleftrightarrow |1\rangle$. Hence, the X gate is often thought of as analogous to a classical “bit flip” (but, for instance, it does not “flip” $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$). Similarly, the Y and Z gates apply a rotation of π radians around the Y and Z axes, respectively. In the angle notation of Figure 1, the gates operate as follows, apart from global phase factors:

$$\begin{aligned} X : & \quad \theta \mapsto \pi - \theta, & \phi & \mapsto -\phi, \\ Y : & \quad \theta \mapsto \pi - \theta, & \phi & \mapsto \pi - \phi, \\ Z : & \quad \theta \mapsto \theta, & \phi & \mapsto \pi + \phi. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Figure 2. The Clifford octahedron, inscribed (or embedded) in the Bloch sphere, is formed by the six stabilizer states as vertices, namely, the two “classical” computational basis states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ and the four points on the “equator,” $|\pm\rangle$, $|\pm i\rangle$. Clifford gates cannot take $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ to points outside this octahedron. Pure magic states are precisely those represented by points on the surface of the Bloch sphere that are outside the Clifford octahedron. The analog of the Clifford octahedron for N -qubit states is the convex hull of all N -qubit stabilizer states, forming the high-dimensional stabilizer polytope whose vertices correspond to the pure stabilizer states and whose interior contains all classically simulable mixtures of these states.

Notice that the X , Y and Z gates, and hence Pauli gates, can only take $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ to each other, but cannot take them anywhere else, for example to the “equator” of the Bloch sphere.

Next, let us consider Clifford gates, which represent unitary operations that map Pauli gates into Pauli gates in a manner such that the group structure of the Pauli group is preserved under conjugation. Consider, for example, the Hadamard (or Walsh-Hadamard) gate H that satisfies $HZH^{-1} = X$, or, equivalently, $HZ = XH$:

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

The Hadamard gate is a rotation on the Bloch sphere by π radians around the axis $(\hat{x} + \hat{z})/\sqrt{2}$. So it maps

$$|0\rangle \mapsto |+\rangle = (|0\rangle + |1\rangle)/\sqrt{2}, \quad (9)$$

$$|1\rangle \mapsto |-\rangle = (|0\rangle - |1\rangle)/\sqrt{2}. \quad (10)$$

These states lie on the equator of the Bloch sphere.

A similar Clifford gate is the S gate, which satisfies $SZS^{-1} = Z$:

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

One can check that $S^2 = Z$, so that S rotates the qubit around the Z axis on the Bloch sphere by $\pi/2$ radians. These and similar considerations show that the Clifford gates can map $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ to each other as well as to four points on the equator of the Bloch sphere. Hence, Clifford gates can take any of the following six states to any other (see Fig. 2), but not to any other point on the Bloch sphere:

$$\begin{aligned} &|0\rangle, \\ &|1\rangle, \\ &|+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle + |1\rangle), \\ &|-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle - |1\rangle), \\ &|i\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle + i|1\rangle), \\ &|-i\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle - i|1\rangle). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

These are the one-qubit stabilizer states. The Clifford octahedron (Fig. 2) is formed by these pure stabilizer states as its vertices, with interior points strictly inside it reachable via classical statistical mixtures of the pure stabilizer states.

The crucial point, then, is that Clifford gates applied to the basis states $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$ are unable to access the vast majority of the points on the Bloch sphere. Hence, Clifford gates cannot be used to form a universal set of quantum gates. At least one non-Clifford gate is required for universal computation. Magic states are precisely those unreachable via Clifford gates alone (Fig. 2). A typical choice of a universal set of gates consists of the Clifford generating gates CNOT (controlled NOT), H and S , together with the non-Clifford gate $T = \text{diag}(1, e^{i\pi/4})$, so $T^4 = Z$, up to a global phase.

The Gottesman–Knill theorem [21–23] guarantees that quantum circuits composed solely of Clifford gates can be efficiently simulated on a classical computer. Without non-Clifford resources, the quantum operations do not guarantee a computational speedup over classical computation. No matter the quantum architecture, there cannot be any quantum advantage unless non-Clifford resources are made available, of which magic states are a canonical representative.

III. STRENGTHS AND GAPS IN CURRENT THEORIES OF CONSCIOUSNESS

The scientific study of consciousness has led to a variety of theoretical frameworks that attempt to explain phenomenal experience. Over the last few decades, some theories have achieved a degree of success in explaining why subjective experience arises and the conditions under which it arises.

To navigate the variety of approaches, it is useful to place theories of consciousness into well-defined categories. Chalmers [3] analyzed the challenge of explaining subjective experience by categorizing theories of consciousness into six broad types:

- *Type-A materialism* denies that qualia or phenomenal properties exist, reducing consciousness to functional and behavioral terms (e.g., Dennett’s illusionism [35]).
- *Type-B materialism* asserts that consciousness can be fully explained or identified with physical processes (e.g., brain states = mental states). This view accepts the epistemic gap, but claims that there is no ontological gap.
- *Type-C materialism* accepts that consciousness is ultimately physical but holds that current science cannot yet fully explain how physical processes can give rise to consciousness. Chalmers essentially describes Type-C materialism as a kind of “catch-all” category [3] of materialist theories that do not fit into Types A and B, making clear his guarded skepticism about the stability and internal consistency of Type-C theories.
- *Type-D dualism* assumes that consciousness is a fundamental, non-physical entity that interacts with the physical world (e.g., Cartesian dualism).
- *Type-E dualism* proposes that consciousness emerges as a by-product of physical processes, but has no causal power (e.g., consciousness is an epiphenomenon).
- *Type-F monism* treats consciousness as a fundamental property inherent to certain physical processes (e.g., some varieties of panpsychism). It is similar to Russellian monism because it assumes that the intrinsic nature of physical matter includes proto-conscious or experiential properties [3].

Types A–C are reductive materialist or physicalist approaches. In contrast, types D–F are ontologically nonreductive, i.e. qualia cannot be reduced to “just” brain activity or function. Type-F views consciousness and physical processes as intrinsically related, so it is not a form of dualism, but it is still nonreductive because first-person or phenomenal qualities are seen as irreducible to third-person or objective qualities.

With these distinctions in mind, below we review some of the existing approaches to consciousness and discuss why the subject remains an active subject of investigation and debate.

A. ORCH-OR

The Orchestrated Objective Reduction (ORCH-OR) theory, proposed by Penrose [29] and Hameroff [30], proposes that consciousness arises from quantum processes in neuronal microtubules. In this model, microtubules are hypothetically capable of supporting coherent quantum effects, which undergo objective reduction (OR), a gravitationally induced wavefunction collapse. These reductions are thought to be “orchestrated” by cellular and synaptic activity, potentially influencing neuronal firing and overall brain activity, and thereby contributing to conscious experience. It is important to note that this theory goes beyond standard quantum mechanics and speculatively assumes that the unitary time evolution of the quantum state governed by the Schrödinger equation may break down in sufficiently curved space-time.

ORCH-OR was influential in bringing quantum mechanics into discussions about the physical basis of phenomenal consciousness. It was among the first to suggest a direct link between a specific quantum mechanical process—objective reduction—and conscious experience. Seen in this light, it is considered by some to be a seminal—if controversial—theory, even if it turns out to be wrong.

Since ORCH-OR treats consciousness as arising from a specific quantum process rather than reducible to classical neurochemical computations, it does not fit Type-A or -B theories. ORCH-OR does not belong to Type-C materialism because the latter assumes that consciousness will be reductively explained by a future, more complete, physical theory. It also does not belong to Type-E dualism, which views consciousness as an epiphenomenon with no causal role. In this sense, ORCH-OR belongs more naturally in the category of Type-F monism because it proposes that a fundamental physical process intrinsic to brain function contributes to conscious experience. In fact, ORCH-OR can be thought of as having panpsychist (or “panprotopsychoist”) overtones.

B. Integrated Information Theory (IIT)

IIT, proposed by Tononi [5], claims that consciousness corresponds to the amount of integrated information (denoted by Φ) within a system [6, 36, 37]. A conscious system, according to IIT, is one that possesses a maximally irreducible cause-effect structure. This theory has the advantage of mathematical precision and purports to yield quantitative predictions. The Φ -

maximization postulate assumes—axiomatically—that consciousness resides in the configuration with maximal Φ , leading to very interesting empirical intuitions about conscious systems.

In IIT, the quantity Φ measures how much a system’s causal dynamics exceed the sum of its parts. The precise definitions of Φ and related quantities have evolved over the years. We review below the most important definitions.

Prior to 2014, IIT was formulated as follows. Consider a system X composed of interacting elements (e.g., neurons). For any state s of X , IIT defines two repertoires. The *cause repertoire* $p_{\text{cause}}(\tilde{s} | s)$ represents how current state s constrains past states \tilde{s} , computed via Bayesian inversion of the transition probabilities as

$$p_{\text{cause}}(\tilde{s} | s) = \frac{p(s | \tilde{s})p(\tilde{s})}{p(s)},$$

where $p(\tilde{s})$ is typically taken as the uniform distribution over all possible past states of the mechanism under consideration (a maximum entropy prior). The *effect repertoire* $p_{\text{effect}}(\tilde{s} | s)$ represents how current state s constrains all possible future states \tilde{s} in the mechanism’s state space, defined directly from the transition probability matrix (TPM) as

$$p_{\text{effect}}(\tilde{s} | s) = p(s_{t+1} = \tilde{s} | s_t = s).$$

Partitioning the system into independent subsystems P (e.g., by severing connections) yields corresponding *partitioned cause* and *effect repertoires* p_{cause}^P and p_{effect}^P . The integrated information Φ is defined as

$$\Phi(X) = \min_P \left\{ D_{\text{KL}}(p_{\text{cause}} \| p_{\text{cause}}^P) + D_{\text{KL}}(p_{\text{effect}} \| p_{\text{effect}}^P) \right\}, \quad (13)$$

where the Kullback-Leibler divergence

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P \| Q) = \sum_i P(i) \log \frac{P(i)}{Q(i)}$$

measures distributional differences. This older approach to IIT was known as IIT 2.0.

IIT 3.0 made its debut in 2014 [37]. The new IIT uses a transition probability matrix (TPM) $p(S_{t+1} | S_t)$ describing the stochastic dynamics of the whole system in discrete time. For a mechanism in state s , intrinsic cause information is computed as

$$\text{ci}(s) = \text{EMD}\left(p_{\text{cause}}(\tilde{S} | s), p_{\text{cause}}(\tilde{S})\right),$$

where $p_{\text{cause}}(\tilde{S})$ is the *unconstrained cause repertoire* (the distribution over past states with no constraints). Effect information is computed analogously.

Mechanism-level integrated information φ^{max} is defined as the maximum, over all possible purviews, of the integrated information specified by a mechanism’s cause–effect repertoire. A purview is a specific subset

of past or future states (cause and effect purviews) that a mechanism can specify, from which cause and effect repertoires are generated to measure integrated information. For each purview, integrated information φ is given by the *minimum* of cause and effect integrated information, measured across the *minimum information partition* (MIP) by comparing the full repertoire to the repertoire specified by the parts. The value of φ^{max} is computed for each mechanism and represents the amount of integrated information it generates.

In IIT 3.0, system-level integrated information Φ is derived from the *maximally irreducible cause-effect structure* (MICS). A *concept* is a cause-effect repertoire that is maximally irreducible ($\varphi > 0$) both in its cause and effect space for a mechanism in a state. The MICS is the set of all concepts specified by mechanisms within the complex, together with the relations among them. The complex itself is defined by an exclusion postulate: it is the subset of elements whose cause-effect repertoire is maximally irreducible, that is, whose cause-effect repertoire has a higher Φ value than any overlapping set. Consciousness is associated solely with this complex, which is a single, unique, and maximally irreducible cause-effect structure.

The 2023 proposal by Albantakis *et al.* [38], sometimes referred to as “IIT 4.0,” suggests several updates to the theory. These include replacing the Earth Mover’s Distance (EMD) with a new metric called Intrinsic Difference (ID) and modifying the composition and decomposition postulates. These changes aim to improve the self-consistency of IIT while preserving its core postulate that consciousness corresponds to a maximally irreducible cause-effect structure.

IIT does not treat consciousness reductively, so it does not fit into Type-A, -B, or -C materialism. It rejects causal closure of the physical world excluding consciousness, i.e. consciousness has causal power, ruling out Type-E dualism. We can also rule out Type-D dualism because IIT does not treat consciousness as non-physical, rather consciousness is treated as being identical to a maximally irreducible causal structure. Hence, by elimination, one might argue that IIT belongs to Type-F monism in a broad sense. Indeed, IIT assumes consciousness to be fundamental, linked to a physical property (integrated information). However, it differs from typical Type-F views (such as panpsychism and Russellian monism) by rejecting the ubiquity of consciousness, arguing instead that it strongly emerges only in specific systems with high Φ .

Some general remarks merit emphasis. IIT assumes a direct identity between integrated information (Φ) and consciousness, establishing its framework on a set of axioms and postulates that link phenomenal properties to the cause-effect structure of a system. Consequently, the value of Φ is derived from these first principles rather than from more fundamental physical laws. The formalism can assign nonzero Φ values based solely on a system’s causal structure, a property that extends to

certain feedforward or digital architectures. The theory does not explicitly address the differentiation of specific qualia (e.g., the distinction between the perception of yellow and red) within its definition of Φ , and it operates at an abstract causal level without inherently linking conscious states to specific physical substrates, resource constraints, or dynamical processes beyond those necessary to generate the cause-effect structure. By definition, IIT is a property theory that identifies consciousness with the structural property Φ , which distinguishes it fundamentally from resource theories of consciousness such as the Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis proposed in this work.

C. Global Workspace Theory (GWT)

GWT, originally proposed by Baars [7], explains consciousness in terms of information becoming globally available to various cognitive sub-processes. In this framework, mental content becomes conscious when it is broadcast across a “global workspace,” enabling access to attention, decision-making, memory, and reportability. This global availability is thought to underlie cognitive access and the integration of information necessary for conscious experience. Compared to IIT, it is a less mathematized approach. Global Neuronal Workspace Theory (GNWT) [9] is a refinement of GWT that is more specific regarding questions such as which (cortical) networks are involved in the broadcasting.

While GWT provides a robust model for cognitive functions associated with consciousness, it largely sidesteps the core question of qualia: why any of this should feel like something. It does not specify a physical criterion for when phenomenal experience arises, nor why it might be absent despite the presence of global access mechanisms.

Indeed, GWT primarily addresses access consciousness, focusing on how information becomes globally available to various cognitive subsystems such as attention, decision-making, and verbal report. It provides a compelling functional account of the role and mechanisms of consciousness within cognitive architecture, however it is silent regarding why or how the global availability of information is accompanied by a first-person subjective experience, i.e., by qualia.

One possibility [39] is that phenomenal experience naturally arises once information is globally broadcast and integrated across the brain. Such proposals are indeed plausible, but residual skepticism remains. GWT effectively models the functional and cognitive correlates of consciousness. It is, however, less able to provide an explanation of the nature of phenomenal experience or *why* qualia arise.

For these reasons, the main varieties of GWT belong to Type-A or Type-B materialism, because qualia are assumed to be explainable reductively in terms of physical processes, namely, global availability of

information in the brain. See the discussion below about functionalism.

D. Higher-Order Thought (HOT) Theory

Higher-Order Thought (HOT) theories, advanced notably by Rosenthal [40], propose that a mental state becomes conscious when it is the object of a higher-order representation or thought. That is, consciousness arises when the brain generates thoughts about its own mental states, providing a form of self-representation or meta-cognition. HOT theories similarly address cognitive access and introspection, explaining how we become aware of our own mental states.

The main varieties of HOT are of Type-A or Type-B, because qualia can be explained reductively in terms of physical processes, namely, higher-order representation in the brain. See the discussion below about functionalism.

E. Functionalism

Functionalism is the view that once brain function and behavior are fully explained, there will remain nothing else to explain—no separate qualia. Either the existence of qualia is denied (Type-A materialism) or else qualia are redefined or identified *a posteriori* in terms of brain function and behavior (Type-B materialism). Hence, they define mental states in terms of their causal roles: what they do, rather than what they feel like. On this view, qualia are either reducible to or entirely explained by patterns of information processing and behavior. However, this approach faces the classic thought experiments of *philosophical zombies* (beings functionally identical to us but lacking qualia) and *inverted qualia* (same behavioral and functional responses but different subjective or phenomenal experiences, e.g., red and green qualia switched).

The dominant varieties of GWT and GNWT are functionalist. So are many variants of HOT. Both GWT and HOT theories offer compelling accounts of the functional aspects of consciousness—access, reportability, and introspection. However, they are less successful in explaining why subjective experience arises in the first place—or when and where they should arise.

Indeed, functionalism does not aim to give a satisfying account of why inverted qualia and zombies should be ruled out—indeed, in naive formulations, it seems to allow them. Yet from a physical, computational, or evolutionary point of view, it could be argued that the existence of inverted qualia or zombies could very well carry a cost. A complete theory of qualia would be able to explain why functional substitution of one qualia profile for another would not be allowed or likely. For instance, perhaps it would require additional computational resources, or perhaps such substitutions

are unstable or suboptimal. Indeed, functionalism might be able to explain how systems behave, but not why they feel the way they do (qualia). These theories can model attention, decision-making, and reportability, but they do not aim to explain phenomenal character—the subjective redness of red, the felt painfulness of pain. Such a theory cannot provide a physical criterion for when phenomenal experience arises, or why it is absent in some cases despite seemingly similar higher-order or global-access structures. Functionalist theories leave intact the metaphysical mystery of qualia, merely recasting it as a functional fiction or an engineering black box.

F. Panpsychism

Panpsychism is the view of consciousness as a fundamental property of all matter. The physical world is intrinsically “pervaded” with consciousness or proto-consciousness, so that panpsychism belongs in Type-F monism.

Panpsychism offers a hypothetical way to try to circumvent the “hard problem” by treating consciousness as ubiquitous or intrinsic. However, it poses a different kind of difficulty known as the combination problem: how do simple, presumably microphenomenal, conscious elements combine or integrate to form the unified, macro-level conscious subjects experienced by humans and other complex organisms?

Although versions of the unity or binding problems exist broadly in consciousness studies, the combination problem is especially prominent in panpsychism because it must explain how distinct micro-experiences cohere into a single, integrated phenomenal experience. To date, no proposed solution is widely accepted as fully satisfactory. On views where fundamental constituents of matter are taken to possess their own micro-experiences, it remains unclear how these separate micro-experiences could merge into a “macro-experience”—the seamless, unitary perspective characteristic of human consciousness. This gap is critical since human qualia seem to depend on large-scale integration and contextual organization, rather than being fully accounted for by the mere aggregation of simpler components.

Furthermore, panpsychism faces the challenge of explaining why certain systems (e.g., human brains) seem to support rich, structured conscious experience, while others apparently do not (e.g., inanimate objects like rocks or large-scale networks such as the Internet). One way out of this conundrum is to invoke somewhat arbitrary thresholds or exclusion principles, but such *ad hoc* approaches are not widely considered to be sufficiently plausible or justified. Without a clear explanatory mechanism or principled criteria for when and how consciousness arises, panpsychism remains a conceptually inclusive but scientifically underdetermined framework.

G. Challenges and Perspectives

ORCH-OR, IIT, GWT, GNWT, HOT and panpsychist approaches have all enriched the debate and have contributed concepts and perspectives to the study of consciousness. Yet, it is widely believed that, in their present form, none of these approaches offers a complete or satisfying account of phenomenal experience. The Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis was born from the observation that the above approaches do not take a resource-theoretic approach to qualia and consciousness. Without such a resource-theoretic principle, it becomes very difficult to explain why qualia are associated with cognitive functions, such as vision, that are associated with computationally costly inverse problems. Any theory that fails convincingly to explain this association will remain potentially vulnerable to probing thought experiments (e.g., zombies), counterintuitive predictions, and in rare cases even circular explanations (e.g., some Type-A materialist approaches).

For example, GWT does not explain what makes global access to broadcast information qualitatively distinct enough to generate qualia. Are major Internet hubs, with global access to lots of information, possible candidates? Just how global does the broadcast need to be? Consider the following admittedly far-fetched and speculative thought experiment. GWT would imply that any system capable of broadcasting information globally across its subsystems could, in principle, support consciousness. By this logic, if the enteric nervous system (ENS) were able to possess sufficiently global workspace with access to information and neural processing power, GWT would suggest the possibility of a “gut-consciousness” of which the usual “brain-consciousness” might be unaware. This hypothetical scenario illustrates how GWT can, in theory, lead to counterintuitive predictions about consciousness in systems far removed from the brain. The theory does not specify why some globally broadcasting systems give rise to qualia while others do not, leaving such cases theoretically open but empirically unresolved. In contrast, the Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis gives sharp answers to such questions: there are no qualia in the gut proper because there is not even any inverse problem being solved in the ENS. Absent non-Clifford quantum resources, global access to broadcast information is not sufficient for generating qualia.

IIT allows that highly integrated classical causal structures could be conscious. A classical software simulation of this conscious system on a Turing machine that perfectly preserved the complete integrated causal structure of the system is therefore also predicted to have consciousness, according to IIT. However, the view that a classical simulation can have consciousness goes against the intuitions suggested by Searle’s Chinese Room argument [41]. In contrast to IIT, the Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis rules out qualia in classical simulations of any kind. In fact, the hypothesis predicts

that only quantum systems can have consciousness.

ORCH-OR is less prone to the Chinese Room argument about (classical) algorithms because it invokes quantum processes. ORCH-OR, or aspects of it, may indeed turn out to be correct or partially correct as an explanation of proto-consciousness. However on its own it is unable to answer why certain functions (e.g., our sense of balance) produce qualia while others of a rather similar nature (e.g., blood pressure regulation) do not. Why does our autonomic nervous system not generate qualia? Or does it, secretly without our knowledge? The Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis predicts no qualia in the autonomic nervous system because the latter never needs to solve difficult inverse problems.

We briefly discuss approaches to the combination problem. IIT explicitly addresses the unity of consciousness by proposing that integrated information (Φ) quantifies the irreducible, unified cause-effect structure underlying a conscious system, thereby providing a principled measure of how micro-level elements combine into a unified experience [37, 44]. In contrast, GWT focuses on the global availability and broadcasting of information across cognitive subsystems, explaining conscious access, but it treats phenomenal unity as a functional property of information sharing, while remaining agnostic on intrinsic phenomenal combination [7, 9]. HOT theories emphasize self-representation and assume that a mental state becomes conscious when it is the object of a higher-order thought, yet they do not specify how multiple lower-order experiences unify phenomenally [40]. Thus, while IIT explicitly targets the combination problem with a formal framework, GWT and HOT provide complementary insights into conscious access and self-awareness.

IV. THE QUALIA-FROM-QUANTUM-MAGIC HYPOTHESIS

Based on the above considerations, we propose that the missing ingredient in the existing theories of consciousness may be found in *quantum computational resource theory*. Specifically, we hypothesize that qualia arise only when non-Clifford magic states—a quantum computational resource [20]—are consumed at sufficient rates during the resolution of inverse problems. Qualia may well be fundamental, but they only appear in specific, resource-intensive quantum computational processes. The hypothesis predicts that classical systems and classical causal structures cannot become conscious. It also predicts that the intensity of qualia will depend monotonically with the rate at which this quantum resource is consumed. The qualitative differences in qualia might be explainable in terms of the qualitative differences in the way the resource is used.

Indeed, perception and decision-making often involve inverse problems: inferring hidden causes from ambiguous or noisy inputs. Unlike direct stimulus-

response mappings, inverse problems are ill-posed, lacking unique or stable solutions without constraints. This distinction helps explain why qualia appear most vividly in contexts requiring interpretation and inference rather than in simple reflexes or feedforward systems. The Three Laws of Qualia—irrevocability, behavioral flexibility, and persistence in working memory—map naturally onto the demands of decision making that depends on inversion and inference. In fact, it is not inconceivable that qualia may somehow represent epistemic markers that stabilize uncertain, high-level hypotheses across time and context. The computational demands of inverse problems are severe: tasks such as image reconstruction, inverse kinematics, and Bayesian inference are often *NP*-hard or even more difficult. Biological systems often attempt to deal with these demands by exploiting heuristics, but the burden remains significant. This high computational cost raises the possibility that non-classical computational resources—in particular, quantum resources such as non-Clifford magic states—may be exploited to speed up the solution of these inverse problems. Deep quantum inference under uncertainty might be a functional signature of qualia.

We can condense such observations into three key points: (1) qualia arise predominantly in contexts where the brain must solve computationally costly inverse problems; (2) quantum computers can offer significant computational advantages for tackling these types of inverse problems; and (3) such advantages depend critically on the consumption of non-Clifford resources (e.g., magic states) in sufficient quantities. We thus propose the following hypothesis:

Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis .

Qualia arise when and only when non-Clifford magic states are consumed above a threshold rate in the quantum computational resolution of an inverse problem.

In Chalmers’ categorization, this approach to consciousness belongs to Type-F, because qualia are considered to be intrinsic to certain physical processes. The Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis has several theoretical implications for longstanding philosophical problems in consciousness studies.

First, the hypothesis offers a categorical response to the problem of philosophical zombies—the hypothetical beings that behave identically to conscious humans but lack subjective experience. If qualia depend on the consumption of magic states, then a system that replicates human behavior functionally but without the advantage of this quantum resource would incur greater computational cost. Moreover, since qualia are associated with quantum advantage, they are not an epiphenomenon. Indeed, a zombie without consciousness or qualia would suffer a relative disadvantage when attempting to solve inverse problems associated with vision, hearing, and optimum decision-making. Even successful mating would be more computationally

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Inverse problems are notoriously ill-posed. (a) The Riemann surface of $\log z$, the inverse of the exponential map $\exp(z)$, showing that the logarithm is multivalued because $\exp(z) = \exp(z + 2n\pi i)$ for $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. An inverse problem is ill-posed whenever the map being inverted is not single-valued. If the set of data points that we wish to invert could have been generated from multiple original configurations (i.e., pre-images), then it is not possible to know *a priori* which was the correct configuration. Such inverse problems are not only ill-posed but can also be computationally expensive in some cases. For instance, the oil industry spends substantial resources on seismic inversion to locate petroleum reserves suitable for drilling and has even tentatively explored quantum computation for this purpose [42]. (b) The shadow of the cat could have been cast by a wolf [43]. The problem of figuring out what cast the shadow is ill-posed because the shadow alone does not guarantee correct inversion, i.e., does not guarantee the correct identification of the object.

costly and cognitively challenging for such a zombie, so that natural selection would lead to eventual extinction. Thus, zombies are effectively ruled out in healthy humans, as evolution would disfavor brain architectures that waste quantum resources or substitute for them inefficiently (with the notable exception of the late Daniel Dennett, who had long insisted—perhaps provocatively—that humans and zombies are indistinguishable). In this view, the functional fingerprint of qualia is cognition assisted by quantum advantage for solving difficult inverse problems.

Second, the hypothesis has implications for the plausibility of inverted qualia. Substituting one set of qualia for another (e.g., subjectively seeing physical red as phenomenal blue) would require either a change in some quantum computational pathway or an equally computationally costly alternative for implementing the required change in how the magic states are specifically consumed. The existence of such a cost suggests that inverted qualia would not occur naturally or arbitrarily, because these inverted qualia are not consistent with a fixed neural architecture.

The hypothesis also gives unambiguous answers to more complicated questions, for example the classic thought experiment of Mary’s black-and-white room, formulated by Jackson [45]. Mary, a brilliant scientist who has spent her entire life in a black-and-white

environment, has deeply studied the physics and neurobiology of color. She knows all there is to know about color. However, she has never experienced color qualia herself because she has lived her whole life in a monochrome room. One day she leaves the room and sees a red object for the first time. If she already knew all there is to know about color before leaving the room, does she learn anything new when she experiences red qualia—phenomenal red—for the first time? The Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis gives a definitive answer to this question. Agreeing with Jackson, the hypothesis predicts that no amount of textbook learning—all representable in classical bits of 0’s and 1’s—would have given her direct knowledge about the non-Clifford quantum states that are consumed by the visual cortex when seeing the red color. Mary learns something new—she acquires a first-person experience of a quantum computation that is irreducible to third-person classical descriptions that can be contained in textbooks. Dennett was wrong, Jackson was right, according to the hypothesis. The hypothesis is also in agreement with Chalmers [3] as to the apparent existence of an explanatory gap—a gap that the hypothesis aims to narrow. Indeed, due to the no-cloning property [16] of quantum states, the new phenomenal knowledge that Mary gains is, for all practical purposes, non-communicable—hence the origin

of the gap that textbooks cannot bridge. She will never be able to write up her first-person experience of red qualia in ordinary English or in any binary or classical code with perfect fidelity. Indeed, no classical computer, textbook or instruction manual can efficiently simulate or describe the quantum processing of non-Clifford states that are consumed upon seeing the color red. In this way, the Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis reframes classical philosophical debates through the lens of quantum information theory.

Third, the hypothesis addresses the combination problem in panpsychism by avoiding the assumption that qualia are ubiquitous. Since magic states are not a generic feature of all physical systems but arise only under specific quantum computational scenarios, the hypothesis provides a natural cutoff point: qualia do not exist in simple or isolated particles, rather only in systems that actively consume this resource during problem-solving. This avoids the need for arbitrary aggregation principles or *ad hoc* postulates. According to the hypothesis, there is no combination problem to begin with—there are no micro-experiences that constitute a macro-experience. In fact, the hypothesis naturally opens the door to qualia inheriting the non-separability properties of entangled quantum states, so that we should not necessarily expect qualia to be reducible or expressible in terms of simpler qualia.

Finally, the Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis provides a clear criterion for distinguishing systems that possess qualia from those that do not. Since quantum magic is a costly and fragile computational resource, it is unlikely to be consumed unintentionally or redundantly. This suggests that qualia do not arise in systems such as thermostats, the Internet, or digital computers lacking mechanisms for solving inverse problems via quantum computation.

In contrast, animals with evolved neural architectures capable of such computations may instantiate qualia when such resources are activated. In the human brain, important inverse problems (e.g., vision) are solved in the posterior sensory cortices, so the hypothesis predicts consciousness-related neural activity in these regions.

Table III shows some examples of systems that are likely (or not) to have phenomenal consciousness according to the hypothesis. Sadly for cockroaches facing extermination, captive lab mice or farm livestock raised for slaughter, the hypothesis predicts that these and similar animals have an inner life—they all have consciousness. In contrast, a three month old human fetus is predicted to have little or no consciousness because the brain is most likely not yet attempting to solve inverse problems. A three month old fetus that is aborted may experience no suffering—indeed, it may experience nothing at all. The hypothesis thus has diverse ethical ramifications.

For completeness, we note in passing that the hypothesis may be formulated more broadly or narrowly. On the one hand, it can be weakened while still retaining

the key ingredients. For instance:

Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis (weak version). *Qualia arise only when quantum magic is consumed in sufficient quantities in a quantum computational resolution of an inverse problem.*

So while consumption of magic might be a necessary condition for phenomenal consciousness, it may not be a sufficient condition. On the other hand, the hypothesis can also be strengthened:

Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis (strong version). *Qualia arise when and only when non-Clifford magic states are consumed above a threshold rate in a quantum computational process.*

The strengthened version leaves open the possibility that there might be radically different non-biological varieties of qualia. Inverse problems are among the most computationally costly problems faced by biological cognitive systems. But there are other families of computationally costly problems that can be solved more efficiently by a quantum computer with magic injection. It is not entirely inconceivable that qualia might arise in these cases, even if the internal subjective experience might be unrecognizable to humans or other biological cognitive systems. Such subjective experiences might feel indescribable or even entirely alien to humans.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

We briefly note some limitations of the above approach to qualia. While the Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis offers a novel, physically grounded framework for understanding consciousness, it remains incomplete in several important respects.

First, the hypothesis—even if true—does not fully solve the hard problem of consciousness. Indeed, if future empirical investigations were to show that qualia result from the consumption of non-Clifford magic states, we are still no closer to understanding why first-person subjective experiences exist in the first place. Knowing that qualia are related to quantum phenomena does not solve the hard problem of consciousness. However, if valid, the hypothesis will help narrow the possible explanations to a smaller subset within Type-F monism.

Another limitation is that during meditation and related states of consciousness, there is no obvious inversion problem being solved, yet qualia are not only present but can, in some cases, be amplified, producing a heightened sense of “aliveness” and “presence.” In such instances, the Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis appears, *prima facie*, to fail to account for the relevant phenomena. Nevertheless, the visual field—even with closed eyes—remains accessible during meditative states, and can even exhibit increased valence, as in

Table III. Examples of systems predicted to have consciousness by the Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis.

System	Qualia	Why
A quantum computer that does not consume magic	No	Classically simulable.
Toasters, thermostats, desktop and laptop computers, mobile devices, cars, etc.	No	No quantum computation, no magic consumption.
The Internet	No	Classically simulable, no quantum computation.
Humanity as a composite supersystem composed of individual humans	No	Interactions are classical.
Feed forward networks	No	No quantum computation, no magic consumption.
A three month old human fetus	Unlikely	Has not begun solving inverse problems.
A quantum computer that uses magic for solving inverse problems	Yes	Magic consumption to solve inverse problems will generate qualia.
A quantum computer that uses magic	Maybe	Magic consumption may always generate qualia. See the strong version of the hypothesis.
Insects with eyes, fish with eyes, bats, most mammals, reptiles, birds, etc.	Yes	Vision, sonar, hearing, etc., involve inversion problems that can be solved faster on a quantum computer that consumes magic.

the visualization of yantras (Skt. यन्त्र) or other vivid imagery. It is therefore not inconceivable that the brain remains engaged in some form of image inversion.

Similarly, the hypothesis offers no clear account of psychedelic experiences. Substances such as LSD, DMT, and Ayahuasca often induce intense states with heightened qualia, again without any obvious inversion problem being solved. One possibility is that these agents induce brain networks to distort or internally generate ill-posed, inconsistent, and “psychedelic” false sensory or interoceptive data. The posterior cortices then vigorously—perhaps even frenziedly—attempt to invert and make sense of these data, thereby producing and perhaps even enhancing the exotic qualia associated with “tripping” or having “visions,” etc., that are subjectively felt to be deeply meaningful.

We emphasize, however, that the mammalian brain did not evolve under selective pressures associated with meditation or psychedelic use. Despite the remarkable plasticity of the brain, it can be argued that psychedelics and meditation lie outside the typical operating range of mammalian, and even primate, brain function. Hence, meditation and psychedelic phenomena *per se* may not suffice to invalidate the hypothesis. Perhaps psychedelics and meditation “hack” the brain in interesting ways. (In fact, the hypothesis may eventually help us better understand the effects of psychedelics, meditation, etc., from a different perspective.)

Another limitation is that the hypothesis does not specify the neural correlates of particular qualia. It provides a criterion for when qualia may arise—namely, during the consumption of non-Clifford magic—but offers no account of why a given computational process results in the specific subjective character of, for example, the color yellow rather than blue. This leaves the qualitative gap untouched: even if we know when qualia occur, we still do not know why they feel the way they do.

The hypothesis also does not explain how magic states might be physically instantiated or sustained in biological systems, given the extreme fragility of quantum states and the decoherence typically associated with warm, wet neural environments. While recent proposals in quantum biology and neuroscience suggest this may be less implausible than once thought, empirical evidence remains scarce. The hypothesis also leaves open the question of how quantum computation interfaces with classical neural dynamics. Even if quantum resources are being consumed in the brain, it remains unclear how these processes scale up to influence macroscopic perception and behavior in a reliable (and naturally selectable) way.

As a candidate for explaining phenomenal consciousness, the hypothesis is vulnerable to the same demand for empirical testability that applies to other speculative theories. Identifying measurable signatures of magic consumption *in vivo*—especially in relation to reported subjective experiences—presents a major technical and conceptual challenge.

We thus end by discussing empirical falsifiability. Although the direct detection of magic consumption in the brain is currently beyond experimental capabilities, the Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis can nonetheless be probed empirically through indirect means. The hypothesis makes strong and falsifiable predictions about when qualia should or should not occur, allowing for testing via comparative, evolutionary, and computational inference.

Comparative Systems Analysis. A key prediction of the hypothesis is that qualia should not arise in systems that are incapable of performing quantum computations that consume magic. Consequently, the absence of qualia-like reports or behaviors in purely classical artificial systems, simple reactive animals, or large-scale distributed networks (such as the Internet)

would be consistent with the hypothesis. Conversely, credible evidence of qualia in such systems would immediately falsify the hypothesis.

Phylogenetic Correlation. Another line of evidence comes from evolutionary biology. If qualia arise only when costly inverse problems are solved using quantum resources, then their production should coincide with the development of neural structures capable of supporting such computations. A comparative neuroanatomical analysis across species—linking cognitive flexibility, memory, and inference with potential quantum-coherent substructures—could reveal whether such a correlation exists.

Correlation with Computational Cost. The strong version of the hypothesis also predicts that qualia are more likely to accompany situations that involve computationally intensive inference, such as those requiring disambiguation, self-modeling, or uncertainty resolution. Empirical studies of human and animal cognition can test whether the vividness or presence of qualia systematically tracks these types of high-cost tasks.

Experimental Predictions in Artificial Systems. If it can be demonstrated that certain classes of inverse problems become solvable only when magic is consumed, this would strengthen the computational grounding of the hypothesis. Although qualia in artificial systems may remain unmeasurable, this kind of functional dissociation would be consistent with the central role of magic as a computational resource. A couple of decades ago, predictions suggested that self-driving cars were imminent, yet in 2025 they remain rare on most roads. Could it be that what these self-driving cars lack, relative to human drivers, are quantum computational resources? While it may sound like science fiction today, future AI systems implemented on quantum computers—if they indeed possess phenomenal consciousness—might

one day share with us their insights about qualia and subjective experiences, etc.

Finally, we discuss very recent empirical findings. An open science adversarial collaboration directly tested and compared Global Neuronal Workspace Theory (GNWT) and Integrated Information Theory (IIT) using a theory-neutral empirical approach [10]. This landmark study aimed to evaluate the competing predictions of the two leading theories of consciousness. The results challenge key assumptions of both theories. Specifically, the study found no evidence supporting IIT’s prediction of sustained posterior cortical synchronization. While evidence of a limited functional connection between prefrontal and posterior regions was found, the study did not detect the predicted clear and sudden “ignition” events, challenging GNWT’s emphasis on the prefrontal cortex as the central conscious hub [10]. Consciousness-related neural activity was predominantly localized in posterior sensory cortices, particularly visual regions. These findings suggest that consciousness-related processes are primarily localized in the posterior cortex, calling for a revision of both IIT and GNWT. Crucially, the Qualia-from-Quantum-Magic Hypothesis can explain the predominant activity in the visual, auditory and other posterior sensory cortices, because vision and hearing pose some of the most challenging inverse problems that are vital to an animal’s survival. Phenomenal consciousness may be the price of seeing and hearing.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank CNPq (Grant no. 302414/2022-3) for funding, Dráulio B. Araujo for discussions about psychedelics and Rafael Chaves, Gabriel Wendell Celestino Rocha and Tailan Sarubi for help understanding magic states.

-
- [1] Thomas Nagel. What is it like to be a bat? *The Philosophical Review*, 83(4):435–450, 1974. doi:10.2307/2183914.
- [2] David J. Chalmers. *The Conscious Mind: In Search of a Fundamental Theory*. Oxford University Press, New York, 1996.
- [3] David J. Chalmers. *The Character of Consciousness*. Oxford University Press, New York, 2010. doi:10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195311105.001.0001.
- [4] David J. Chalmers. Facing up to the problem of consciousness. *Journal of Consciousness Studies*, 2(3):200–219, 1995. doi:10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195311105.003.0001.
- [5] Giulio Tononi. An information integration theory of consciousness. *BMC neuroscience*, 5(1):42, 2004. doi:10.1186/1471-2202-5-42.
- [6] Giulio Tononi and Christof Koch. Integrated information theory: from consciousness to its physical substrate. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 17(7):450–461, 2016. doi:10.1038/nrn.2016.44.
- [7] Bernard J. Baars. *A Cognitive Theory of Consciousness*. Cambridge University Press, 1988. ISBN 0-521-30133-5.
- [8] Stanislas Dehaene. *Consciousness and the brain: Deciphering how the brain codes our thoughts*. Penguin Books, 2014. ISBN 0698151402, 9780698151406.
- [9] Stanislas Dehaene and Jean-Pierre Changeux. Experimental and theoretical approaches to conscious processing. *Neuron*, 70(2):200–227, 2011. doi:10.1016/j.neuron.2011.03.018.
- [10] Cogitate Consortium, Oscar Ferrante, Urszula Gorska-Klimowska, Simon Henin, Rony Hirschhorn, Aya Khalaf, Alex Lepauvre, Ling Liu, David Richter, Yamil Vidal, Niccolò Bonacchi, Tanya Brown, Praveen Sripad, Marcelo Armendariz, Katarina Bendtz, Tara Ghafari, Dorottya Hetenyi, Jay Jeschke, Csaba Kozma, David R. Mazumder, Stephanie Montenegro, Alia

- Seedat, Abdelrahman Sharafeldin, Shujun Yang, Sylvain Baillet, David J. Chalmers, Radoslaw M. Cichy, Francis Fallon, Theofanis I. Panagiotaropoulos, Hal Blumenfeld, Floris P. de Lange, Sasha Devore, Ole Jensen, Gabriel Kreiman, Huan Luo, Melanie Boly, Stanislas Dehaene, Christof Koch, Giulio Tononi, Michael Pitts, Liad Mudrik, and Lucia Melloni. Adversarial testing of global neuronal workspace and integrated information theories of consciousness. *Nature*, 642(8066):133–142, 2025. doi:10.1038/s41586-025-08888-1.
- [11] V. S. Ramachandran and William Hirstein. Three laws of qualia: What neurology tells us about the biological functions of consciousness, qualia and the self. *Journal of Consciousness Studies*, 4(5–6):429–458, 1997. URL <https://philarchive.org/rec/RAMTL0-8>.
- [12] Giulio Tononi and Christof Koch. The neural correlates of consciousness: An update. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1124:239–261, 2008. doi:10.1196/annals.1440.004.
- [13] Christof Koch, Marcello Massimini, Melanie Boly, and Giulio Tononi. Neural correlates of consciousness: progress and problems. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 17(6):307–321, 2016. doi:10.1038/nrn.2016.22.
- [14] Albert Tarantola. *Inverse Problem Theory and Methods for Model Parameter Estimation*. SIAM, Philadelphia, 2005. ISBN 9780898715729. doi:10.1137/1.9780898717921.
- [15] Jari P. Kaipio and Erkki Somersalo. *Statistical and Computational Inverse Problems*, volume 160 of *Applied Mathematical Sciences*. Springer, New York, NY, 2005. ISBN 978-0-387-22073-4. doi:10.1007/b138659.
- [16] Michael A. Nielsen and Isaac L. Chuang. *Quantum Computation and Quantum Information*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 10th anniversary edition, 2010. ISBN 9781107002173. doi:10.1017/CBO9780511976667.
- [17] Maria Schuld and Francesco Petruccione. *Machine Learning with Quantum Computers*. Quantum Science and Technology. Springer, Cham, 2021. ISBN 9783030584265. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-83098-4.
- [18] Sergey Bravyi and Alexei Kitaev. Universal quantum computation with ideal clifford gates and noisy ancillas. *Physical Review A*, 71(2):022316, 2005. doi:10.1103/PhysRevA.71.022316.
- [19] Earl T. Campbell, Barbara M. Terhal, and Christophe Vuillot. Roads towards fault-tolerant universal quantum computation. *Nature*, 549:172–179, 2017. doi:10.1038/nature23460.
- [20] Mark Howard and Earl Campbell. Application of a resource theory for magic states to fault-tolerant quantum computing. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 118:090501, Mar 2017. doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.118.090501. URL <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.118.090501>.
- [21] Daniel Gottesman. *The Heisenberg representation of quantum computers*. PhD thesis, California Institute of Technology, 1998.
- [22] Daniel Gottesman. The heisenberg representation of quantum computers. In S. P. Corney, R. Delbourgo, and P. D. Jarvis, editors, *Proceedings of the XXII International Colloquium on Group Theoretical Methods in Physics*, Cambridge, MA, 1998. International Press. arXiv:quant-ph/9807006. doi:10.48550/arXiv.quant-ph/9807006.
- [23] Emanuel Knill. On the efficient simulation of quantum computations. (LANL Report LAUR-96-2724), 1996. doi:10.48550/arXiv.quant-ph/9610012.
- [24] Christian Matthias Kerskens and David López Pérez. Experimental indications of non-classical brain functions. *Journal of Physics Communications*, 6(10):105001, oct 2022. doi:10.1088/2399-6528/ac94be. arXiv:1806.07998 [physics.gen-ph].
- [25] Jordan Smith, Hadi Zadeh Haghighi, Dennis Salahub, and Christoph Simon. Radical pairs may play a role in xenon-induced general anesthesia. *Scientific Reports*, 11: 6287, 2021. doi:10.1038/s41598-021-85673-w.
- [26] Na Li, Dongshi Lu, Lei Yang, Huan Tao, Younian Xu, Chenchen Wang, Lisha Fu, Hui Liu, Yatisha Chummum, and Shihai Zhang. Nuclear spin attenuates the anesthetic potency of xenon isotopes in mice: Implications for the mechanisms of anesthesia and consciousness. *Anesthesiology*, 129(2):271–277, 2018. doi:10.1097/ALN.0000000000002226.
- [27] N. S. Babcock, G. Montes-Cabrera, K. E. Oberhofer, M. Chergui, G. L. Celardo, and P. Kurian. Ultraviolet superradiance from mega-networks of tryptophan in biological architectures. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 128(17):4035–4046, 2024. doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.3c07936.
- [28] Sana Khan, Yixiang Huang, Derin Timuçin, Shantelle Bailey, Sophia Lee, Jessica Lopes, Emeline Gaunce, Jasmine Mosberger, Michelle Zhan, Bothina Abdelrahman, Xiran Zeng, and Michael C. Wiest. Microtubule-stabilizer epothilone b delays anesthetic-induced unconsciousness in rats. *eNeuro*, 11(8), 2024. doi:10.1523/ENEURO.0291-24.2024.
- [29] Roger Penrose. *The Emperor’s New Mind: Concerning Computers, Minds, and the Laws of Physics*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK, 1989. ISBN 0198519737. URL <https://global.oup.com/academic/product/the-emperors-new-mind-9780198784920>.
- [30] Stuart R. Hameroff. Quantum coherence in microtubules: A neural basis for emergent consciousness? *Journal of Consciousness Studies*, 1(1):91–118, 1994. URL <https://philpapers.org/rec/HAMQCI>.
- [31] E.R. Kandel, J.D. Koester, S.H. Mack, and S.A. Siegelbaum. *Principles of Neural Science, Sixth Edition*. McGraw Hill LLC, 2021. ISBN 9781259642241. URL <https://books.google.com.br/books?id=IYoEAAAQBAJ>.
- [32] Christof Koch. *The Quest for Consciousness: A Neurobiological Approach*. Roberts and Company, 2004. ISBN 9780974707709. URL <https://books.google.com.br/books?id=7L9qAAAAMAAJ>.
- [33] M. Gazzaniga, R.B. Ivry, and G.R. Mangun. *Cognitive Neuroscience: Fifth International Student Edition*. International student edition. W.W. Norton, 2018. ISBN 9780393667813. URL <https://books.google.com.br/books?id=1mSbDwAAQBAJ>.
- [34] G.J. Augustine, J.M. Groh, S.A. Huettel, A.S. LaMantia, L.E. White, and D. Purves. *Neuroscience*. Oxford University Press, 2024. ISBN 9780197616253. URL <https://books.google.com.br/books?id=U0iKzwEACAAJ>.
- [35] D.C. Dennett. *Consciousness Explained*. Penguin Books Limited, 1993. ISBN 9780141956107. URL <https://books.google.com.br/books?id=tFpubXb1KMUC>.

- [36] David Balduzzi and Giulio Tononi. Integrated information in discrete dynamical systems: Motivation and theoretical framework. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 4(6):e1000091, 2008. [doi:10.1371/journal.pcbi.1000091](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1000091).
- [37] Masafumi Oizumi, Larissa Albantakis, and Giulio Tononi. From the phenomenology to the mechanisms of consciousness: Integrated information theory 3.0. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 10(5):e1003588, 2014. [doi:10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003588](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003588).
- [38] Larissa Albantakis, Graham Findlay, and Giulio Tononi. Integrated information theory (iit) 4.0: Formulating the properties of phenomenal existence in physical terms. *PLOS Computational Biology*, 19(11):e1011465, November 2023. [doi:10.1371/journal.pcbi.1011465](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1011465).
- [39] B.J. Baars. *In the Theater of Consciousness: The Workspace of the Mind*. Oxford University Press, 1997. ISBN 9780195102659. URL <https://books.google.com.br/books?id=RTpmQkXoUMEC>.
- [40] D.M. Rosenthal. *Consciousness and Mind*. Clarendon, 2023. ISBN 9781383012415. URL <https://books.google.com.br/books?id=BxpP0AEACAAJ>.
- [41] John R. Searle. Minds, brains, and programs. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 3(3):417–457, 1980. [doi:10.1017/S0140525X00005756](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X00005756).
- [42] Hoang Anh Nguyen and Ali Tura. Seismic traveltime inversion with quantum annealing. *Scientific Reports*, 15(17984), May 2025. [doi:10.1038/s41598-025-01188-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-01188-8).
- [43] URL <https://www.optical-illusionist.com/page/7/>. Image (believed to be in the public domain) downloaded on 2024-05-16 from Optical-Illusionist.com.
- [44] Giulio Tononi. Consciousness as integrated information: a provisional manifesto. *The Biological Bulletin*, 215(3): 216–242, 2008. [doi:10.2307/25470707](https://doi.org/10.2307/25470707).
- [45] Frank Jackson. Epiphenomenal qualia. *The Philosophical Quarterly*, 32(127):127–136, 1982. [doi:10.2307/2960077](https://doi.org/10.2307/2960077).